

With Concern Numbers $A_{3,n}$ [Where $A_{3,n} = 3^{2^n} + 2$ And n Is An Integer ≥ 0]; And A Glance On Numbers Of The Form $k + F_n$, Where $k \in \{2, 4, 8\}$ And F_n Is A Fermat Number

Ikorong Annouk¹

¹Research In Pure Mathematics, France

Abstract and Definitions

We denote by $A_{3,n}$, the number of the form $3^{2^n} + 2$, where n is an integer ≥ 0 ; in other words, for every integer $n \geq 0$, $A_{3,n} = 3^{2^n} + 2$ [it is easy to check that $A_{3,0} = 5$, $A_{3,1} = 11$, $A_{3,2} = 83$, $A_{3,3} = 6563$ and $A_{3,4} = 43046723$; moreover, for every $j \in \{0,1,2,3\}$, $A_{3,j}$ is prime and $A_{3,4}$ is composite (since $A_{3,4} \equiv 0 \pmod{19}$)]. In this paper, we show [via elementary arithmetic congruences] the following result (T.). For every positive integer n such that $n \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$, we have $A_{3,n} - 2 \equiv 17 \pmod{19}$; and for every integer $n \geq 2$, we have $A_{3,n} - 2 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$. Result (T.) immediately implies that there are infinitely many composite numbers of the form $A_{3,n}$. That being so, using result (T.) coupled with a special case of a Theorem of Dirichlet on arithmetic progressions, we explain why it is natural to conjecture that there are infinitely many prime numbers of the form $A_{3,n}$. A Fermat number is a number of the form $F_n = 2^{2^n} + 1$, where n is an integer ≥ 0 . A Fermat composite (see Dickson (1952) or Hardy, & Wright, (1979) or Annouk, (2012)) is a non prime Fermat number and a Fermat prime is a prime Fermat number. Fermat composites and Fermat primes are characterized via divisibility in Annouk, (2012) and in Annouk, (2014). It is known (see [4]) that for every $j \in \{0,1,2,3,4\}$, F_j is a Fermat prime ($F_0 = 2^{2^0} + 1 = 3$ and 3 is prime, $F_1 = 2^{2^1} + 1 = 5$ and 5 is prime, $F_3 = 2^{2^3} + 1 = 257$ and 257 is prime, and $F_4 = 2^{2^4} + 1 = 65537$ and 65537 is prime), and it is also known (see Hardy, & Wright (1979) or Hoffman (2000) or Křížek, et al. (2002) or Keller, (2020) or Euler, (1738) or Scharlau, & Opolka, (1985) that F_5 and F_6 are Fermat composites ($F_5 = 2^{2^5} + 1 = 641 \times 6700417$, and since 2013, it is known that $F_{2747497} = 2^{2^{2747497}} + 1$ is Fermat composite number). Fermat numbers have importance and their application to other sciences such as cryptography, neural networks, electronic computer, polygons with straightedge, filtering, autocorrelation, and related areas with conventional computing are clearly known. Factorization of Fermat numbers (specially for big one) is a very hard problem in number theory and cryptography too. The biggest known Fermat prime is $F_4 = 2^{2^4} + 1 = 65537$, and this number is used in cryptography because of the fact that this prime helps the cryptography less vulnerable to the public exponent attack lowly (as mentioned "Coppersmith's short pad attack" in the literature). Practical and efficient methods are still in need for factorization of such numbers, even there are many algorithms to factorize some of such composite numbers. That being so, in this paper, we show [via elementary arithmetic congruences] the following result (E.). For every integer $n > 0$ such that $n \equiv$

Article History:

Received: 29.08.2025

Revised: 27.09.2025

Accepted: 06.10.2025

Published: 11.10.2025

Citation: Annouk, I. (2025). With Concern Numbers $A_{3,n}$ [Where $A_{3,n} = 3^{2^n} + 2$ And n Is An Integer ≥ 0]; And A Glance On Numbers Of The Form $k + F_n$, Where $k \in \{2,4,8\}$ And F_n Is A Fermat Number. *European Journal of Science and Modern Technologies*, 1(5), 54-61. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2025.1\(5\).06](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2025.1(5).06)

© The Author(s) 2025. Published by [AMO Publisher](https://www.amopublisher.com). This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted reuse, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

$1 \pmod{2}$, we have $F_n - 1 \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$; and for every integer $n \geq 2$, we have $F_n - 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$, where $j \in \{3,5\}$. Result (E.) immediately implies that there are infinitely many composite numbers of the form $2 + F_n$. Result (E.) also implies that the only prime of the form $4 + F_n$ is 7 and the only primes of the form $8 + F_n$ are twin primes 11 and 13. That being said, using result (E.) and a special case of a Theorem of Dirichlet, we conjecture that there are infinitely many primes of the form $2 + F_n$.

Keywords: $A_{3,n}$, Fermat numbers, F_n .

AMS Classification 2000: 05xx and 11xx.

Introduction

This paper is divided into two simple Section. In Section.1, we show Result (T.) stated in Abstract and Definitions and a consequence of this Result. Moreover, using Result (T.) coupled with a special case of a Theorem of Dirichlet on arithmetic progressions (we recall that Dirichlet's Theorem, also called the Dirichlet prime number theorem, states that "for any two positive coprime integers a and d, there are infinitely many primes of the form $a + nd$, where n is also a positive integer. In other words, there are infinitely many primes that are congruent to a modulo d"), we explain why it is natural to conjecture that there are infinitely many prime numbers of the form $A_{3,n}$ (numbers $A_{3,n}$ are explicated in Abstract and Definitions). In Section.2, we show Result (E.) stated in Abstract and Definitions and some consequences of this Result. Moreover, using Result (E.) coupled with a special case of a Theorem of Dirichlet on arithmetic progressions, we explain why it is natural and not surprising to conjecture that there are infinitely many prime numbers of the form $2 + F_n$, where F_n is a Fermat number (Fermat numbers are explicated in Abstract And Definitions).

Regarding $A_{3,n}$ [Where $A_{3,n} = 3^{2^n} + 2$ And n Is An Integer ≥ 0]

Theorem 1.1. We have the following.

(T.) For every integer $n \geq 0$ such that $n \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$, we have $A_{3,n} - 2 \equiv 17 \pmod{19}$.

(T'.) For every integer $n \geq 2$, we have $A_{3,n} - 2 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$.

(T''). There are infinitely many composite numbers of the form $A_{3,n}$.

That being said, to prove Theorem 1.1, we need the following remarks.

Remark 1.2. $(-2)^{64} \equiv 17 \pmod{19}$.

Proof. Indeed observing that

$$(-2)^{64} = (256)^8 \text{ and } 256 \equiv 9 \pmod{19} \tag{1.1}$$

and using (1.1), then it becomes immediate to deduce that

$$(-2)^{64} \equiv (9)^8 \pmod{19} \tag{1.2}$$

Now noticing that

$$(9)^8 = (81)^4 \text{ and } 81 \equiv 5 \pmod{19} \tag{1.3}$$

and using ((1.3),(1.2)), then it becomes immediate to deduce that

$$(-2)^{64} \equiv (5)^4 \pmod{19} \tag{1.4}$$

That being said, observing that

$$(5)^4 = 625 \text{ and } 625 \equiv 17 \pmod{19} \quad (1.5)$$

and using ((1.5),(1.4)), then it becomes immediate to deduce that $(-2)^{64} \equiv 17 \pmod{19}$.

Remark 1.3. Let n be an integer ≥ 10 . If $3^{2^{n-6}} \equiv 17 \pmod{19}$, then $(3^{2^{n-6}})^{2^6} \equiv 17 \pmod{19}$.

Proof. Indeed observing (via the hypotheses) that

$$3^{2^{n-6}} \equiv 17 \pmod{19} \quad (1.6)$$

and noticing that

$$2^6 = 64 \text{ and } 17 \equiv (-2) \pmod{19} \quad (1.7)$$

then using ((1.6), (1.7)), we immediately deduce that

$$(3^{2^{n-6}})^{2^6} \equiv (-2)^{64} \pmod{19} \quad (1.8)$$

Clearly $(3^{2^{n-6}})^{2^6} \equiv 17 \pmod{19}$ [use (1.8) and Remark 1.2].

Proposition 1.4. Let n be an integer > 0 such that $n \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$; then $3^{2^n} \equiv 17 \pmod{19}$.

Proof. Otherwise

$$\text{let } n \text{ be minimum such that} \quad (1.9),$$

$$3^{2^n} \not\equiv 17 \pmod{19} (n \equiv 4 \pmod{6} \text{ and } n > 0) \quad (1.9')$$

Clearly

$$n \geq 10 \quad (1.10)$$

(since $3^{2^4} = (81)^4 = 43046721$ and $43046721 \equiv 17 \pmod{19}$). It is immediate to see that

$$3^{2^n} = (3^{2^{n-6}})^{2^6} \quad (1.11)$$

Now using equality (1.11) and inequality (1.10), we easily deduce that (1.9) and (1.9') clearly imply that

$$(3^{2^{n-6}})^{2^6} \not\equiv 17 \pmod{19} \text{ where} \quad (1.12)$$

$$3^{2^{n-6}} \equiv 17 \pmod{19} (n \equiv 4 \pmod{6}; n \geq 10) \quad (1.12')$$

(1.12) and (1.12') clearly contradict Remark 1.3.

Proposition 1.5. Let n be an integer > 0 such that $n \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$. Then $A_{3,n} \equiv 0 \pmod{19}$ and $A_{3,n}$ is composite [recall (see Abstract and Definitions) that $A_{3,n} = 3^{2^n} + 2$].

Proof. Clearly

$$3^{2^n} + 2 \equiv 0 \pmod{19} \quad (1.13)$$

[observe (via Proposition 1.4) that $3^{2^n} \equiv 17 \pmod{19}$ and use elementary arithmetic congruences]. So $A_{3,n} \equiv 0 \pmod{19}$ and $A_{3,n}$ is composite [use congruence (1.13) and observe that $3^{2^n} + 2 = A_{3,n}$ and $A_{3,n} > 19$ (note that $n \geq 4$, since n is an integer > 0 such that $n \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$)]. Proposition 1.5 immediately follows.

Remark 1.6. There are infinitely many composite numbers of the form $A_{3,n}$ or there are infinitely many prime numbers of the form $A_{3,n}$.

Proof. Immediate.

Remark 1.7. Let n be an integer ≥ 3 . If $3^{2^{n-1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$, then $3^{2^{n-1}} \times 3^{2^{n-1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$.

Proof. Immediate [via elementary arithmetic congruences].

Remark 1.8. Let n be an integer ≥ 2 ; then $3^{2^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$.

Proof. Otherwise

$$\text{let } n \text{ be minimum such that } 3^{2^n} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{5} (n \geq 2) \quad (1.14)$$

Clearly

$$n \geq 3 \quad (1.15)$$

(since $3^{2^2} = 81$ and $81 \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$). It is immediate to see that

$$3^{2^n} = 3^{2^{n-1}} \times 3^{2^{n-1}} \quad (1.16)$$

Now using equality (1.16) and inequality (1.15), we easily deduce that (1.14) clearly implies that

$$3^{2^{n-1}} \times 3^{2^{n-1}} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{5}, \text{ where } 3^{2^{n-1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{5} \text{ and } n \geq 3 \quad (1.17)$$

(1.17) clearly contradicts Remark 1.7.

Having made the previous Remarks and Propositions, then Theorem.1.1 becomes immediate to prove.

Proof of Theorem 1.1.

(T.) Immediate [use Proposition 1.4 and observe that $A_{3,n} - 2 = 3^{2^n}$].

(T'.) Immediate [use Remark 1.8 and observe that $A_{3,n} - 2 = 3^{2^n}$].

(T''). Immediate [use Proposition 1.5 and Remark 1.6].

Now using Theorem 1.1, then we end this Section with this observation about numbers $A_{3,n}$ which are prime.

Using (T'.) of Theorem 1.1 and a special case of a Theorem of Dirichlet on arithmetic progressions (we recall that Dirichlet's Theorem, also called the Dirichlet prime number theorem, states that "for any two positive coprime integers a and d , there are infinitely many primes of the form $a + nd$, where n is also a positive integer. In other words, there are infinitely many primes that are congruent to a modulo d "), we explain why it is natural to conjecture that there are infinitely many primes of the form $A_{3,n}$ [notice (see Abstract and Definition) that for every for every $j \in \{0,1,2,3\}$, $A_{3,j}$ is prime].

Observation. It is natural to conjecture that there are infinitely many primes of the form $A_{3,n}$.

Indeed observing [via (T'.) of Theorem 1.1] that

$$\text{For every integer } n \geq 2, \text{ we have } A_{3,n} - 2 \equiv 1 \pmod{5} \quad (1.18)$$

clearly

$$A_{3,n} \equiv 3 \pmod{5} \text{ for every integer } n \geq 2 \quad (1.19)$$

[use (1.18) and elementary arithmetic congruences].

It is immediate that

$$A_{3,n} \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \text{ for every integer } n \geq 0 \quad (1.20)$$

[observe (via the definition of $A_{3,n}$) that that $A_{3,n} = 3^{2^n} + 2$ and use elementary arithmetic congruences].

So

$$A_{3,n} \equiv 3 \pmod{5} (n \text{ integer } \geq 2) \text{ and} \quad (1.21)$$

$$A_{3,n} \equiv 2 \pmod{3} (n \text{ integer } \geq 0) \quad (1.21')$$

[use (1.19) and (1.20)].

Now let

$$D_{3,5} = \{e; e \text{ is prime and } e \equiv 3 \pmod{5}\}$$

and

$$D_{2,3} = \{e; e \text{ is prime and } e \equiv 2 \pmod{3}\};$$

look at $D_{3,5}$ and $D_{2,3}$. Since it is immediate that

$$(3,5) = 1 \text{ and } (2,3) = 1, \text{ i.e.} \quad (1.22)$$

$$(3,5) \text{ and } (2,3) \text{ are two couple of positive coprime integers} \quad (1.22')$$

then using (1.22) and (1.22') coupled with a special case of a Theorem of Dirichlet on arithmetic progressions (we recall that Dirichlet's Theorem, also called the Dirichlet prime number theorem, states that "for any two positive coprime integers a and d , there are infinitely many primes of the form $a + nd$, where n is also a positive integer. In other words, there are infinitely many primes that are congruent to a modulo d "), it immediately follows that

$$\text{card}(D_{3,5}) \text{ is infinite and } \text{card}(D_{2,3}) \text{ is infinite} \quad (1.23)$$

Using (1.21) and (1.21') and (1.23) and the fact that for every $j \in \{0,1,2,3\}$, $A_{3,j}$ is prime and $A_{3,j} \in D_{3,5} \cup D_{2,3}$ [use Abstract and Definition for $(A_{3,j})$, and use (1.21) and (1.21') and the definition of $(D_{3,5}, D_{2,3})$], then it becomes naturel to conjecture the following.

Conjecture. $D_{3,5} \cup D_{2,3}$ contains infinitely many numbers of the form $A_{3,n}$ ($D_{3,5}$ and $D_{2,3}$ are defined via the Observation placed just above).

Remarking [by the definition of $(D_{3,5}, D_{2,3})$] that $D_{3,5}$ is an infinite set of prime numbers and $D_{2,3}$ is an infinite set of prime numbers, then it becomes trivial to see that the previous conjecture immediately implies that there are infinitely many primes of the form $A_{3,n}$.

Regarding $k + F_n$, Where $k \in \{2, 4, 8\}$ And F_n Is A Fermat Number

Theorem 2.1. We have the following.

(E.) For every integer $n > 0$ such that $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, we have $F_n - 1 \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$; and for every integer $n \geq 2$, we have $F_n - 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$, where $j \in \{3,5\}$.

(E.1) There are infinitely many composite numbers of the form $2 + F_n$.

(E.2) The only prime of the form $4 + F_n$ is 7 and the only primes of the form $8 + F_n$ are twin primes 11 and 13.

To prove Theorem 2.1, we need the following remarks.

Remark 2.1. Let n be an integer > 1 such that $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. If $2^{2^{n-2}} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$, then $2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$.

Proof. Immediate [indeed observe (via elementary arithmetic congruences) that $2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \equiv 256 \pmod{7}$ (since $2^{2^{n-2}} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$) and $256 \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$].

Proposition 2.2. Let n be an integer > 0 such that $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$; then $2^{2^n} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$.

Proof. Otherwise

$$\text{let } n \text{ be minimum such that } 2^{2^n} \not\equiv 4 \pmod{7}, \text{ where} \tag{2.1}$$

$$n \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \text{ and } n > 0 \tag{2.1'}$$

Clearly

$$n \geq 3 \tag{2.2}$$

(since $2^{2^1} = 4$ and $4 \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$). It is immediate to see that

$$2^{2^n} = 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \tag{2.3}$$

Now using equality (2.3) and inequality (2.2), we easily deduce that (2.1) and (2.1') clearly imply that

$$2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \times 2^{2^{n-2}} \not\equiv 4 \pmod{7}; 2^{2^{n-2}} \equiv 4 \pmod{7} \text{ where} \tag{2.4}$$

$$n \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \text{ and } n > 1 \tag{2.4'}$$

(2.4) and (2.4') clearly contradict Remark 2.1.

Remark 2.3. Let n be an integer ≥ 3 . If $2^{2^{n-1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$ where $j \in \{3,5\}$, then $2^{2^{n-1}} \times 2^{2^{n-1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$.

Proof. Immediate [via elementary arithmetic congruences].

Proposition 2.4. Let n be an integer ≥ 2 ; then $2^{2^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$, where $j \in \{3,5\}$.

Proof. Otherwise

$$\text{let } n \text{ be minimum such that } 2^{2^n} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{j} \text{ where } j \in \{3,5\} \tag{2.5}$$

Clearly

$$n \geq 3 \tag{2.6}$$

(since $2^{2^2} = 16$ and $16 \equiv 1 \pmod{j}$ where $j \in \{3,5\}$). It is immediate to see that

$$2^{2^n} = 2^{2^{n-1}} \times 2^{2^{n-1}} \tag{2.7}$$

Now using equality (2.7) and inequality (2.6), we easily deduce that (2.5) clearly implies that

$$2^{2^{n-1}} \times 2^{2^{n-1}} \not\equiv 1 \pmod{j}, \text{ where } j \in \{3,5\} \text{ and where} \tag{2.8}$$

$$2^{2^{n-1}} \equiv 1 \pmod{j}; n \geq 3 \tag{2.8'}$$

(2.8) and (2.8') clearly contradict Remark 2.3.

Proposition 2.5. Let n be an integer ≥ 3 such that $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$. Then $2 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$ and $2 + F_n$ is composite.

Proof. Clearly

$$2 + (2^{2^n} + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{7} \quad (2.9)$$

[observe that $2^{2^n} \equiv 4 \pmod{7}$ (use Proposition 2.2) and use elementary arithmetic congruences]. So $2 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{7}$ and $2 + F_n$ is composite [use congruence (2.9) and observe that $2 + (2^{2^n} + 1) = 2 + F_n$ and $2 + F_n > 7$ (note that $n \geq 3$)]. Proposition 2.5 immediately follows.

Proposition 2.6. Let n be an integer ≥ 2 . Then $4 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $4 + F_n$ is composite.

Proof. Clearly

$$4 + (2^{2^n} + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{3} \quad (2.10)$$

[observe that $2^{2^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$ (use Proposition 2.4) and use elementary arithmetic congruences]. So $4 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$ and $4 + F_n$ is composite [use congruence (2.10) and observe that $4 + (2^{2^n} + 1) = 4 + F_n$ and $4 + F_n > 3$ (note that $n \geq 2$)]. Proposition 2.6 immediately follows.

Proposition 2.7. Let n be an integer ≥ 2 . Then $8 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ and $8 + F_n$ is composite.

Proof. Clearly

$$8 + (2^{2^n} + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{5} \quad (2.11)$$

[observe that $2^{2^n} \equiv 1 \pmod{5}$ (use Proposition 2.4) and use elementary arithmetic congruences]. So $8 + F_n \equiv 0 \pmod{5}$ and $8 + F_n$ is composite [use congruence (2.11) and observe that $8 + (2^{2^n} + 1) = 8 + F_n$ and $8 + F_n > 5$ (note that $n \geq 2$)]. Proposition 2.7 immediately follows.

Remark 2.8. There are infinitely many composite numbers of the form $2 + F_n$ or there are infinitely many prime numbers of the form $2 + F_n$.

Proof. Immediate.

Having made the previous Remarks and Propositions, then Theorem 2.1 becomes immediate to prove.

Proof of Theorem 2.1.

(E.). Immediate [use Proposition 2.2 and Proposition 2.4 and observe that $2^{2^n} = F_n - 1$].

(E.1). Immediate [use Proposition 2.5 and Remark 2.8].

(E.2). Clearly the only prime of the form $4 + F_n$ is 7 [observe that $4 + F_0 = 7$ and $4 + F_1 = 9$ and use Proposition 2.6]; and clearly the only primes of the form $8 + F_n$ are twin primes 11 and 13 [observe that $8 + F_0 = 11$ and $8 + F_1 = 13$ and use Proposition 2.7].

Now usig Result (E.), then we end this paper by looking at numbers of the form $2 + F_n$ which are prime [observe that for every $n \in \{0,1,2,4\}$, $2 + F_n$ is prime and $2 + F_3$ is not prime].

Observation. It is natural to conjecture that there are infinitely many primes of the form $2 + F_n$.

Indeed observing [via Result (E.) of Theorem 2.1] that

$$F_n - 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \text{ and } F_n - 1 \equiv 1 \pmod{5} \text{ for every integer } n \geq 2 \quad (2.12),$$

clearly

$$2 + F_n \equiv 4 \pmod{5} \text{ and } 2 + F_n \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \text{ for every integer } n \geq 2 \quad (2.13)$$

[use (2.12) and elementary arithmetic congruences].

Now let

$$Q_{4.5} = \{e; e \text{ is prime and } e \equiv 4 \pmod{5}\}$$

and let

$$Q_{1.3} = \{e'; e' \text{ is prime and } e' \equiv 1 \pmod{3}\}$$

Since it is immediate that

$$(4,5) = 1 \text{ and } (1,3) = 1 \quad (2.14)$$

then using (2.14) coupled with a special case of a Theorem of Dirichlet on arithmetic progression (we recall that Dirichlet's Theorem, also called the Dirichlet prime number theorem, states that "for any two positive coprime integers a and d , there are infinitely many primes of the form $a + nd$, where n is also a positive integer. In other words, there are infinitely many primes that are congruent to a modulo d "), it follows that

$$\text{card}(Q_{4.5}) \text{ is infinite and } \text{card}(Q_{1.3}) \text{ is infinite} \quad (2.15)$$

Now using (2.13) and (2.15), then it becomes natural to conjecture the following.

Conjecture. $Q_{4.5}$ or $Q_{1.3}$ contains infinitely many numbers of the form $2 + F_n$ ($Q_{4.5}$ and $Q_{1.3}$ are defined via the Observation placed just above).

The previous conjecture immediately implies that there are infinitely many primes of the form $2 + F_n$

References

- Annouk, I. (2012). Placed near the Fermat primes and the Fermat composite numbers. *International Journal of Research in Mathematics and Applied Mathematical Sciences*, 3, 72–82.
- Annouk, I. (2014). Then we characterize primes and composite numbers via divisibility. *International Journal of Advanced in Pure Mathematical Sciences*, 2(1).
- Deza, E. (Year unknown). *Mersenne Numbers and Fermat Numbers* (Moscow State Pedagogical University, Russia).
- Dickson, L. E. (1952). *History of the theory of numbers. Vol. I: Divisibility and primality* (Preface III–Preface XII). New York, NY: Chelsea Publishing Company.
- Euler, L. (1738). Observations on a theorem of Fermat and others on looking at prime numbers.
- Hardy, G. H., & Wright, E. M. (Year unknown). *An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers* (5th ed.). Oxford, UK: Clarendon Press.
- Hoffman, P. (2000). *Erdős, l'homme qui n'aimait que les nombres* (pp. 30–49). Paris, France: Éditions Belin.
- Keller, W. (2020). Prime factors of Fermat numbers and complete factoring status. Retrieved from <http://www.prothsearch.com/2020>
- Křížek, M., Luca, F., Somer, L., & Šolcová, A. (2002). *Lectures on Fermat Numbers: From Number Theory to Geometry* (CMS Books in Mathematics, 2nd ed.).
- Scharlau, W., & Opolka, H. (1985). *From Fermat to Minkowski: Lectures on the theory of numbers and its historical development*. New York, NY: Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-1867-6>

